

OPTIMUM DESIGN OF FIBROUS LAMINATED HYBRID COMPOSITES WITH REQUIRED FLEXURAL STIFFNESS

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ABSTRACT

An optimum design method of fibrous laminated hybrid composites with required flexural stiffness is proposed. Flexural lamination parameters for hybrid composites which consist of a high stiffness surface composite and a low stiffness core composite are introduced and the behavior of the parameters is investigated. A cost-minimum solution can be obtained from the condition that the feasible design region on the lamination parameter plane converged into a point. The optimum laminate construction is obtained after a few iteration of calculations on a desk-top computer.

INTRODUCTION

Fibrous composites are often referred to as "Tailored materials" since their mechanical properties such as strength and stiffness can be varied by changing the constituent materials and geometric configurations of reinforcements. Optimum material design methods for such tailored materials have been studied for the maximum bending stiffness¹, maximum in-plane strength², maximum bending strength³, maximum buckling strength⁴ and maximum fundamental frequency⁵. But, the method for the minimum cost under required stiffnesses has not been studied so far.

A minimum cost problem under a constraint about the stiffness can be, in general, converted to a maximum stiffness problem under a constraint about the cost. However, such a conversion cannot be performed when the constraint is made with respect to more-than-one stiffnesses of composites. This paper treats such a case.

FLEXURAL STIFFNESS OF HYBRID LAMINATES

The laminated hybrid composites intended for this study are sandwich-type plates with a high stiffness surface composite and a low stiffness core composite, shown in Fig. 1. The stacking sequence is symmetric, the surface and core have two ply groups, respectively, and each ply group has same fiber orientation angle of $\pm\theta_i$ where i is the ply group index. Two ply groups in each part are used because they are necessary and sufficient for designing flexural stiffness⁶.

Fig. 1
Laminated hybrid composite
intended for the analysis.

The normalized flexural stiffness D_{ij}^* ($i, j=1, 2, 6$ where 1 and 2 mean the reference axes for the plate and 6 means shear in the reference system) is presented by

$$D_{ij}^* = \frac{12D_{ij}}{h^3} = \frac{24}{h^3} \int_0^{h/2} Q_{ij} z^2 dz = \frac{24}{h^3} \sum_{k=1}^4 Q_{ij}^{(k)} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} z^2 dz \quad (1)$$

where Q_{ij} ($i, j=1, 2, 6$) is the modulus of the ply group. The above equation can be rewritten:

$$D_{ij}^* = \sum_{k=1}^4 \mu_k Q_{ij}^{(k)} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\mu_k = R_k^3 - R_{k-1}^3, \quad R_k = \frac{2z_k}{h} \quad (3)$$

The ratio R_k is the thickness ratio of the core.

Tsai et al. presented the following expression to evaluate the modulus, Q_{ij} , by introducing the invariants U of the modulus⁷.

$$\begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} \\ Q_{22} \\ Q_{12} \\ Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} U_1 & \cos 2\theta & \cos 4\theta \\ U_1 & -\cos 2\theta & \cos 4\theta \\ U_4 & 0 & -\cos 4\theta \\ U_5 & 0 & -\cos 4\theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Substituting Eq.(4) into Eq.(2) yields

$$\begin{bmatrix} D_{11}^* \\ D_{22}^* \\ D_{12}^* \\ D_{66}^* \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} U_1 & W_{1c}^* & W_{2c}^* & W_{1s}^* & W_{2s}^* \\ U_1 & -W_{1c}^* & W_{2c}^* & -W_{1s}^* & W_{2s}^* \\ U_4 & 0 & -W_{2c}^* & 0 & -W_{2s}^* \\ U_5 & 0 & -W_{2c}^* & 0 & -W_{2s}^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ U_{2c} \\ U_{3c} \\ U_{2s} \\ U_{3s} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where

$$U_m = R_2^3 U_{mc} + (1 - R_2^3) U_{ms} \quad (m=1,2,3,4,5) \quad (6)$$

$$W_{1c}^* = \mu_1 \cos 2\theta_1 + \mu_2 \cos 2\theta_2 \quad (7)$$

$$W_{2c}^* = \mu_1 \cos 2\theta_1 + \mu_2 \cos 2\theta_2 \quad (7)$$

$$W_{1s}^* = \mu_3 \cos 2\theta_3 + \mu_4 \cos 2\theta_4 \quad (8)$$

$$W_{2s}^* = \mu_3 \cos 2\theta_3 + \mu_4 \cos 2\theta_4 \quad (8)$$

OPTIMUM DESIGN METHOD

1. Formulation for Optimum Design

The cost of a hybrid plate is minimized here under the constraints on the thickness and stiffness D_{ij}^* or a function of D_{ij}^* of the plate. A proposed method is illustrated by adopting the effective flexural stiffnesses, $E_1^f I$, $E_2^f I$ and $E_6^f J$, as the constraint functions where E_1^f and E_2^f are the effective Young's moduli for 1 and 2-axes bending, E_6^f is the effective shear modulus for 1 or 2-axis torsion, and I and J are the moment of inertia and the polar moment of inertia, respectively. Then the thickness of the plate can be assumed to be constant and the constraints can be considered in terms of effective moduli E_1^f , E_2^f and E_6^f because the thickness always becomes the upper limit value. For sandwich-type hybrid plates an expensive and high-stiffness composite is often used as the surface. Consequently, the objective function of the cost-minimum problem may be the core thickness ratio R_c which is maximized. Then the optimum problem is written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Find the orientation angles and stacking ratios of the ply groups} \\ &\text{such that Maximize } R_c \\ &\text{subject to } E_1^f \geq E_{10}^f \quad (E_{10}^f: \text{const.}, \quad i=1,2,6) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

2. Flexural Lamination Parameters of Laminated Hybrids

The factors W_{1c}^* , W_{2c}^* , W_{1s}^* , and W_{2s}^* in Eqs (7) and (8) are called flexural lamination parameters of hybrid composites, FLPH in short, in this paper. The feasible region of FLPH's is investigated first since the region yields the possible design region of the hybrid composites shown in Fig. 1 Utilizing Eqs. (7) and (8) yields

$$W_{2c}^* \leq R_c^3 \quad W_{2c}^* \geq 2W_{1c}^{*2}/R_c^3 - R_c^3 \quad (10)$$

$$W_{2s}^* \leq 1 - R_c^3 \quad W_{2c}^* \geq 2W_{1s}^{*2}/(1 - R_c^3) - (1 - R_c^3) \quad (11)$$

Fig. 2 The feasible regions of FLPH's (flexural lamination parameters of hybrid composites) Left: core material, Right: surface material.

Figure 2 shows the feasible regions of FLPH's when $R_c=0.7$.

The constraint region imposed by Eq. (9) is obtained by drawing the contour lines of the effective flexural moduli on the FLPH planes. E_1^f , for instance, is written as:

$$E_1^f = (D_{11}^* D_{22}^* - D_{12}^{*2}) / D_{22}^* \quad (12)$$

The expression for the contour line of E_1^f can be presented as follows:

$$W_{2S}^* = A W_{1S}^{*2} + B W_{1S}^* + C \quad (13)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} A &= U_{2S}^2 / (U_{3S} K_1), \quad K_1 = 2U_1 + 2U_4 - E_1^f \\ B &= -(E_1^f - 2U_{2C} W_{1C}^*) U_{2S} / K_1 \\ C &= -(E_1^f - 2U_{2C} W_{1C}^*) U_{2C} W_{1C}^* / K_1 - U_{3C} W_{2C}^* + K_2 / K_1 \\ K_2 &= U_1 E_1^f - U_1^2 + U_4^2 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The expressions for the contour lines of E_2^f and E_6^f are obtained similarly. Fig. 3 shows a constraint region where the surface and core materials are Graphite/Epoxy and Glass/Epoxy, respectively (their material constants are shown in Table 1), and $E_1^f=60$, $E_2^f=30$, $E_6^f=10$ (GPa), $R_c=0.7$, $W_{1C}^*=0$, $W_{2C}^*=0$. The shaded region shows the design region. The core composite is made isotropic in this case since $W_{1C}^*=W_{2C}^*=0$.

Fig. 3 The design region presented on the surface FLPH plane. The values of the core FLPH's are shown as small circle. The constraints on the effective flexural moduli are shown.

Table 1 Material constants⁷ (GPa)

Material	U1	U2	U3	U4	U5
CFRP(T300/5208)	76.37	85.73	19.71	22.61	26.88
GFRP(Scotchply1002)	20.47	15.40	3.33	5.53	7.47

Each contour lines moves with changing in R_c , W_{1c}^* and W_{2c}^* , and the feasible regions also change their size with changing in R_c . Consequently, the design region will converged into a point when R_c is maximized. The optimum FLPH's can be obtained from this condition. The optimum orientation angles of the ply groups can be calculated from Eqs. (7) and (8) where μ can be given appropriately considering the number of plies.

3. Optimum Design Procedure

The algorithm proposed is as follows:

Step 1: Draw FLPH diagram for $R_c=0$, $W_{1c}^*=W_{2c}^*=0$.

Step 2: Change W_{1c}^* and W_{2c}^* such that the design region is maximized.

Step 3: Redraw FLPH diagram after increasing R_c . If the design region disappears go to Step 3 with the increment of R_c being decreased.

Step 4: Go to Step 2. If the design region converges into a point in spite of the operation in Step 2 the optimum solution is obtained.

These steps are carried forward interactively with the graphic interface of a computer. The design region moves linearly without changing its shape when W_{1c}^* and W_{2c}^* are changed. Therefore, the operation in Step 2 is very simple. The typical values of W_{1c}^* and W_{2c}^* , namely, $(R_c^3, R_c^3), (0, -R_c^3)$ and $(-R_c^3, R_c^3)$, are necessary and sufficient in Step 2.

The steps above can be performed automatically with a computer, but a manual operation is suitable because the time for obtaining the optimum solution is only a few minutes for the operation and the operator or designer can understand the relation between the constraints and the optimum solution.

Fig. 4 The situation where the design region is reduced to a point, that is, the core thickness ratio R_c is maximized.

Figure 4 shows the situation where the design region converges into a point and the core thickness ratio R_c is maximized. The maximum value is 0.854, but $R_c=0.85$ can be realized when the half number of plies is $N=20$, for instance, because R_c should be a multiple of $1/N$. The values of W_{1c}^* and W_{2c}^* are chosen arbitrary unless the converged point is outside the feasible region of FLPH's. For this example the orientation angles θ_1 and θ_2 are put to zero. The value of FLPH's are obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{1c}^* &= 0.614, & W_{2c}^* &= -0.614, & W_{1s}^* &= 0.07, & W_{2s}^* &= 0.14 \\ R_c &= 0.85 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The orientation angles θ_1 through θ_4 are calculated from Eqs.(7) and (8) giving an appropriate value of μ . Utilizing Eqs.(7) and (8) yields

$$\theta_1 = \frac{1}{2} \cos^{-1} T_1, \quad \theta_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cos^{-1} T_2 \quad (16)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} T_1 &= (-K_b \pm \sqrt{K_b^2 - K_a K_c}) / K_a, \quad T_2 = (W_{1c}^* - \mu_1 T_1) / \mu_2 \\ K_a &= 2\mu_1(\mu_1 + \mu_2), \quad K_b = -2\mu_1 W_{1c}^* \\ K_c &= 2W_{1c}^{*2} - \mu_2 W_{2c}^* - \mu_2(\mu_1 + \mu_2) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$$\theta_3 = \frac{1}{2} \cos^{-1} T_3, \quad \theta_4 = \frac{1}{2} \cos^{-1} T_4 \quad (18)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} T_3 &= (-L_b \pm \sqrt{L_b^2 - L_a L_c}) / L_a, \quad T_4 = (W_{1s}^* - \mu_3 T_1) / \mu_4 \\ L_a &= 2\mu_3(\mu_3 + \mu_4), \quad L_b = -2\mu_3 W_{1s}^* \\ L_c &= 2W_{1s}^{*2} - \mu_4 W_{2s}^* - \mu_4(\mu_3 + \mu_4) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

For the case shown in Fig. 4 the calculated values are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_1 &= 0, \quad \theta_2 = 0, \quad R_1 \text{ has no meaning.} \\ \theta_3 &= 18.53, \quad \theta_4 = 75.25, \quad R_3 = 0.95 \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, the stacking sequence is presented as follows:

$$[(\pm 75.25^\circ)_1^{\text{CFRP}} / (\pm 18.53^\circ)_2^{\text{CFRP}} / (0^\circ)_{17}^{\text{GFRP}}]_S \quad (20)$$

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) Flexural lamination parameters of sandwich-type hybrid composites are introduced and the flexural stiffness can be expressed using these parameters.
- (2) A design region where the constraints are imposed on the flexural stiffness or a function of it can be clarified on the flexural lamination parameter plane.
- (3) The optimum solution can be obtained by making the design region converge into a point.
- (4) The stacking sequences of $[0^\circ]_S$, $[\pm 45^\circ]_S$ and $[90^\circ]_S$ often are sufficient for core composites.

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